

THE STATE CADASTRE FOR THE REGULATION OF INFORMATION RESOURCES FOR THE FORMATION AND IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Based on the socio-economic reforms implemented in our republic and the national model of development based on this, systematic analysis, analogues, mutual comparison, comparative analysis and calculation methods are widely used in the article.

Key words: building, structure, cadastre, information resources, cadastral serial number, name, location, typological relevance, date.

INTRODUCTION

The fundamental essence of the reforms implemented in the economy of our republic is to increase the well-being of the population and fundamentally improve their social and economic situation [1,10].

Therefore, the creation of various buildings and structures, which are the basis of the social life of the population, the registration of various rights to them in the state register, the maintenance of quantitative and qualitative accounting and the evaluation of these data in terms of value, as well as the generally accepted order, in a specific manner covering in the documents, providing the real estate market that is being formed in the country with this information is one of the issues of important practical importance. In order to solve these problems, the state cadastre of buildings and structures is maintained within the unified system of state cadastres [1,2,6,7].

In fact, in the "Regulation on the procedure for maintaining the state cadastre of buildings and structures" adopted in accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of

Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 278 of June 2, 1997, it is recognized that "The state cadastre of buildings and structures ensures the effective use and protection of buildings and structures, the property owners and it is maintained to ensure that the rights of other users of these objects, as well as the ownership of individually constructed buildings and structures and other material rights are transferred from the state register" [1,2,7,12,16,20].

It is known that the built buildings and structures were built in the cities, urban-type settlements and villages of our Republic, and they differ depending on their essence, importance and other characteristics. According to the information provided by the State Committee "Ergeodezkadastr", the State Committee "Architectural Construction" and other official agencies, today there are 120 cities, 113 urban-type and more than 10-11 thousand rural settlements in the territory of our country. there are residential buildings, non-residential buildings and structures [3,4,11,12,13]. These buildings and structures are considered the national wealth of the country and are owned and used by legal entities and individuals, foreign legal entities and individuals on the basis of various property and material rights. It is important to maintain the state cadastre of buildings and structures in order to rationally and efficiently organize this use, improve the tax system, positively solve mortgage issues, insurance and other market problems.

METHODS

It should be noted that the application of geoinformation systems in the cadastre system or cartography is a relatively young field, so it is appropriate to analyze the researches of foreign scientists in this direction. In particular, A.M. Berlyant, I.K. Lure, S.N. Serbanyuk, N.V. Konovalova, E.G. Kapralov, Yu.F. Kiyajnikov, Ya.E. Smirnov, and V.V. Artyomenko worked and got a number of positive results and formed important scientific-practical conclusions.

Among the Uzbek scientists on the use of geoinformation systems in cartography, E.Yu. Safarov and M.S. The Ghulomovas are also doing some scientific work. However, there are not enough scientific developments and practical recommendations based on the use of such modern systems in the cadastral system, specifically the cadastral system of buildings and structures.

THE MAIN PART

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2013 No. 1989 "On measures for the further development of the National Information and Communication System of the Republic of Uzbekistan" within the

framework of the "Electronic Government" system, the project "Creation of the Real Estate Cadastre Registration Information System" was implemented in 2013-2017 implementation has been established [1,9,10,11] in organizing the management of the cadastre of buildings and structures, it is important to automate it, that is, to create an automated cadastre information system (AAT). AAT is created to address the following issues:

- Automation of preparation and registration of legal documents of buildings and structures;
- Creating and maintaining the state cadastre of buildings and structures;
- Creating and maintaining a database of land, buildings and structures of settlements;
- Automation of performance of functional tasks assigned to regional services of real estate cadastre, accounting information of objects:
 - Cadastral order number;
 - Name;
 - Location;
 - Typological relevance;
 - To set the date;
 - The name and address of the legal or physical person who is the owner, owner, user or renter;
 - Departmental affiliation of the object;
 - The purpose of the object;
 - Historical data;
 - Reconstruction and losses that changed the original appearance of the object;
 - Repair works (general description, cost, time, author, place of storage of documents);
 - Information about the transfer of rights to the building, structure, land plot from the state register;
 - Includes boundaries of protection zones and construction regulation zones (plan based on approval document, brief description).

The location of buildings and structures, their ownership to legal entities and individuals with property rights or other material rights, the grounds and terms of the emergence of these rights, their suspension periods, conditions for limiting property rights and other material rights, information on the rights of third parties to these objects, buildings and information on the legal status of the facilities is considered [1,3,4,5].

The value of buildings and structures, their use characteristics, the production goals of these objects, their use for the specified purposes and other information form the basis of the economic status of buildings and structures.

Conformity of buildings and structures to land development schemes, master plans of cities, settlement projects, as well as requirements of urban development norms and rules, parameters of buildings (floors, general, living, production areas), occupied land plot, date of construction, engineering and technical the availability of communications, seismic resistance and other technical data are the architectural-construction status of buildings and structures [14,15,16].

State land cadastre, state cadastre of buildings and structures, as well as an automated computer database on the state registration of rights to real estate:

At the republican level - in the Central Information and Analysis Center of the Republic of the National Center of Geodesy and Cartography;

It is formed in the "Information-analytical centers" of territorial land formation and real estate cadastre services in the regions [17,18,19].

The Republican Central Information and Analysis Center updates the central database every month and provides basic information about real estate objects in electronic form on the Internet.

The right to ownership of information in the central database and the relationship between their owners are regulated by the Law on Information.

Information in the central database is presented to users in the national language. Provision of information in the central database to users in other languages is carried out based on the agreement of the parties.

Presentation and transmission of information in the central database to users, distribution in the network is carried out on the basis of a contract in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan (except for information considered a state secret or confidential).

Real estate information related to the applicant's rights and legal interests shall be provided free of charge to state bodies and property owners upon their request.

"Information-Analysis Centers" are responsible for the accuracy of the information in the database of the Central Information-Analysis Center of the Republic.

Provision of confidential information and public (basic) information to users shall be carried out in the order specified in this Order and other regulatory documents.

Information included in the state secret or confidential information category may be provided to users only with the permission of the relevant state authorities.

Personal information of legal entities or individuals may be provided to users with their consent.

CONCLUSION

This article analyzes the general situation of the cadastre of buildings and structures maintained in the administrative area, studies the state of creation and maintenance of the database, and develops suggestions and recommendations for the geodetic and cartographic maintenance of the state cadastre of buildings and structures as follows:

It was determined that the state cadastre of buildings and structures consists of district and city cadastral registers, cadastral maps and plans, cadastral documents and geofunds, as well as computer data generated in the prescribed manner, and its maintenance is carried out in the following three stages:

Stage 1 - collecting information on the legal, economic and architectural-construction status of buildings and structures at the district, city level and recording them in the cadastral register;

Stage 2 - drawing up a cadastral plan and map of objects;

Stage 3 - creation of a computer database, taking into account the information obtained in the previous stages.

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